

Revision of Requirements 2026-2028: Public Feedback

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Introduction

The CoreTrustSeal Board is pleased to welcome community suggestions for revisions to the CoreTrustSeal Requirements. We are a peer managed and operated organization that only thrives with input and assistance from our community.

To maintain alignment with practice and to ensure the requirements meet community needs, the requirements are subject to feedback and revision every three years. **The new Requirements (v04.00) will be in place from 2026-2028. All existing certifications under the current (v03.00) requirements remain valid until due for renewal.**

At the last revision of Requirements a significant number of changes were made, both structural and textual, to improve clarity and maintain alignment with the repository and data infrastructure landscape (see <https://zenodo.org/records/7051237>). The proposed changes from the Board that follow will aim to be minimal for stability purposes, as the CoreTrustSeal mission continues to be provision of a low barrier to entry 'core' level of requirements that is broadly applicable to repository data service providers ensuring the long term preservation of the digital objects they curate for the benefit of a defined designated community.

Thus, the broad scope of the requirements, the self-assessment statements, and the evidence required to meet them will remain as steady as possible. Any changes made will be clearly communicated.

The Board welcomes feedback on any of its proposals from the community including general comments and those related to specific requirements. Although we will do our best, please be aware we cannot provide individual answers to your feedback. If necessary, a firm draft revision will be shared for additional feedback in September.

The estimated duration of this questionnaire is 20 minutes. It will be active until August 15th 2025. Thank you for your time and feedback!

The CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board

Printed copy of this questionnaire: [CoreTrustSeal TDR Requirements v0.01 2026 2028](#). Follow this link for a printed copy of this survey if you would like to prepare comments/suggestions for survey response to the Trustworthy data repository requirements review 2026-2028.

2023-2025 Requirements can be found here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7051011>

Administrative information:

The CoreTrustSeal is responsible for the collection and processing of the answers. (contact : info@coretrustseal.org)

Sciences Po is providing support over the questionnaire tool. (contact : dpo@sciencespo.fr)

Questions for Respondents

Information Collection

- Are you responding on behalf of a CoreTrustSeal Certified Repository?
 - Yes/No
- If a CoreTrustSeal Certified Repository, please provide the Repository name
 - Text box
- If you are not from a CoreTrustSeal Certified repository are you considering CoreTrustSeal?
 - Yes/No/In the process of preparing an application/not in scope for CoreTrustSeal
- Organization Name
 - Text box
- Organisation contact Email
 - Text box
- Area of Professional Expertise
 - Text box

Supporting Evidence

The amount of public evidence made available varies across applications. The Board is seeking community feedback on what should constitute minimum or ideal evidence for each Requirement.

Requirements

Q9 - Background Information

Level of Curation

- A.** Content distributed as deposited
- B.** Basic curation – e.g. brief checking, addition of basic metadata or documentation
- C.** Enhanced curation – e.g. conversion to new formats during ingest, enhancement of documentation and metadata
- D.** Data-level curation – as in C above, but with additional editing of deposited data

Board Proposals: The Board proposes to replace the name “Level of Curation” by “Level of Curation and Preservation” and change the levels with “A. Active preservation”, “B. Initial Curation”, “C. Deposit Compliance” and “D. Content distributed as deposited. Unattended deposit-storage-access” as per the Position Paper (<https://zenodo.org/records/11476980>) published in 2024. Guidance will be amended accordingly, and additional explanations will be provided. The Board welcomes community feedback on these points.

Do you agree? Yes /No. If no give Community feedback box

Q10 - Other Relevant Information

Board Proposals:The Board welcomes community feedback on other information that will provide useful context about the repositories applying for certification. What do you want to tell us? What do we need to know?

Do you agree? Yes /No. If no give Community feedback box

Organizational Infrastructure

Q11- Mission & Scope (R01)

R01. The repository has an explicit mission to provide access to and preserve data in its domain.

Guidance:

Repositories take responsibility for the curation of digital objects, and for ensuring that materials are held in the appropriate environment for appropriate periods of time. For Trustworthy Repositories it must be clear to depositors and users that active preservation of and continued access to the digital objects is an explicit role of the repository.

The response statement and evidence should include references to the following items:

- The mission to actively preserve and provide access to digital objects
- The level of approval that the mission has received.

Evidence for this Requirement could include an approved public mission statement, roles mandated by funders, or a policy statement signed off by a governing board.

Board Proposals: The Board recommends to change the headline of this requirement to “The repository has an explicit mission to provide access to and actively preserve data in its domain”, to add an explicit mention of active preservation, and welcomes community feedback.

Do you agree? Yes /No. If no give Community feedback box

Q12- Rights Management (R02)

R02. The repository maintains all applicable rights and monitors compliance.

Guidance:

The repository manages, and communicates to relevant stakeholders, all rights (permissions, prohibitions, obligations) covering data and metadata deposit, storage, preservation, access, and use.

This requirement relates to the system, methods and artefacts (e.g. licenses, agreements, terms and conditions, and related policies and procedures) in place for rights management.

The repository must obtain all necessary rights from the depositor, and demonstrate that there are sufficient controls in place to ensure they are applied and monitored.

The response statement and evidence should include references to the following items:

- The overall rights management approach to deposited files, data and metadata.
- The rights to copy, transform, and store digital objects for preservation, as well as provide

access to them

- Conditions of use (e.g. intellectual property rights, distribution, intended use, protection of sensitive data, etc.).
- Deposit and access agreements or licenses.
- How rights metadata is managed for humans (e.g. license documents/files) or machines.
- Monitoring of compliance at deposit, during curation/preservation, and during access and reuse. Describe any circumstances where compliance monitoring is not possible.
- Measures in place if non-compliance is detected.

Data and metadata, including 'open data', will usually have some rights attached even if there is no signed license artefact or formal agreement in place. This could include obligations such as citation and attribution of data and metadata used, or making secondary analysis openly available. If all data and metadata are made available without any conditions of access or use then this should be made clear in the response statement.

Rights negotiations and transfer should be described under Deposit & Appraisal (R08). Any ethical codes of conduct, privacy measures, or legislation that influence rights management should be described under Legal & Ethical (R04).

Board Proposals: None, the Board welcomes community feedback.

Do you agree? Yes /No. If no give Community feedback box

Q13 - Continuity of Service (R03)

R03. The Repository has a plan to ensure ongoing access to and preservation of its data and metadata.

Guidance:

The repository must have measures in place to address the risks inherent in changing circumstances, including in mission and/or scope. This Requirement covers the stable management of repository services over time (business continuity) and the response when services have problems (disaster recovery). It also includes preparations for handover of digital objects and services to another repository (succession planning). The deposit, storage, preservation, and access services offered by the repository to depositors and users are all in scope.

The response statement and evidence should include references to the following items:

- The functions and services offered by the repository to depositors and users.
- The approach to rapid changes of circumstance and long-term planning.
- The options for relocation or transition of the activity to another repository. For example, the case of cessation of funding due to an unexpected withdrawal of funding, or a shift of host institution interests.
- The repository approach to managing policies, procedures and other business information over time.

Even though succession agreements may be hard to achieve it is important to acknowledge the possibility that a repository will cease to function or exist. If there is no formal, written

agreement between the repository and a successor then the compliance level cannot be higher than "In Progress: the repository is in the implementation phase".

Any technical aspects of business continuity, and disaster and succession planning should be covered in R15 (Technical infrastructure).

Board Proposals: None, the Board welcomes community feedback.

Do you agree? Yes /No. If no give Community feedback box

Q14 - Legal & Ethical (R04)

R04. The repository ensures to the extent possible that data and metadata are created, curated, preserved, accessed and used in compliance with legal and ethical norms.

Guidance:

This requirement relates to repository awareness and processes around legal and ethical issues, including privacy and confidentiality, that impact the creation, curation, and use of digital objects.

To maintain the trust of those who agree to have their digital objects held by the repository, evidence should demonstrate practices that reflect the legal status and sensitivity of digital objects, including guidance for depositors and users.

The response statement and evidence should include references to the following items:

- How the repository identifies and manages relevant legal and ethical standards that impact operations.
- Compliance with specific legal and/or ethical discipline or domain standards.
- Information requested from depositors to confirm that data collection or creation was carried out in accordance with legal and ethical criteria in the relevant geographical location or discipline (e.g. Ethical Review Committee/Institutional Review Board or Data Protection legislation).
- Any data or metadata with disclosure risk e.g. depositor/user information, personal, cultural, or environmental information

For applicants that hold data or metadata with disclosure risk include references to the following items:

- Special procedures applied to manage disclosure risk
- Conditions of distribution, access protection and use
- Processes to review disclosure risk and to take the necessary steps to either anonymize files or to provide access in a secure way
- Staff training in the management of digital objects with disclosure risk.
- Guidance provided on the responsible deposit, download, and use of disclosive or potentially disclosive data and metadata.

The management of related rights and compliance checks should be covered under Rights (R02). Measures to protect digital objects should be addressed under Security (R16).

Board Proposals: None, the Board welcomes community feedback.

Do you agree? Yes /No. If no give Community feedback box

Q15 - Governance & Resources (R05)

R05. The repository has adequate funding and sufficient numbers of staff managed through a clear system of governance to effectively carry out the mission.

Guidance:

This Requirement reflects a need for transparency of financing, governance, responsibilities, and decision making. Evidence should demonstrate that the repository has a clear system of governance and sufficient human and financial resources to carry out its mission.

The response statement and evidence should include references to the following items:

- Descriptions and diagrams of governance bodies, groups and hierarchies.
- Timescales for provision and renewal of funding for operational costs and recruitment; it is understood that permanent, ongoing funding cannot be perfectly quantified or guaranteed.
- Evidence that the repository is, or is hosted by, a recognized institution (supporting long-term stability and sustainability) appropriate to its Designated Community.
- Demonstrate that the repository can meet its obligations, including sufficient funding, staff resources, IT resources, and a budget for external engagement when necessary.

The availability of appropriate expertise is covered under Expertise (R06) below.

Board Proposals: The Board suggests that an organisational diagram would be helpful to the reviewers in understanding the different partners and responsibilities, and welcomes community feedback.

Do you agree? Yes /No. If no give Community feedback box

Q16 - Expertise & Guidance (R06)

R06. The repository adopts mechanisms to secure ongoing expertise, guidance and feedback-either in-house, or external.

Guidance:

A repository must identify the skills necessary to deliver the services it offers, and source and maintain those skills either as internal resources or through external engagement. An effective repository strives to accommodate evolutions in data types, data volumes, and data rates, as well as to adopt the most effective new technologies in order to remain valuable to its Designated Community.

The response statement and evidence should include references to the following items:

- That guidance and expertise reflects the scientific scope of the repository, if relevant.
- The repository aligns internal recruitment and external engagement with the services it offers.
- The repository ensures that its staff have access to ongoing training and professional development.
- The range and depth of expertise of both the organisation and its staff, including any

relevant affiliations (e.g. national or international bodies), is appropriate to the mission.

- In-house advisers, or external advisory committees that include technical, curation, data science, data security, and disciplinary experts.
- How the repository communicates with experts for advice.

Board Proposals: None, the Board welcomes community feedback.

Do you agree? Yes /No. If no give Community feedback box

Digital Object Management

Q17 - Provenance and authenticity (R07)

R07. The repository guarantees the authenticity of the digital objects and provides provenance information.

Guidance:

The repository should provide evidence to show that it operates a data and metadata management system that maintains provenance information to ensure authenticity from deposit, and through curation and preservation to the point of access.

Any intentional changes to data and metadata should be documented, including the rationale and originator of the change. Authenticity covers reliability and provenance, including the relationship between the deposited digital objects and those provided at the point of access.

The response statement and evidence should include references to the following items:

- The repository approach to changing and versioning data and metadata. How the approach and records of changes are communicated to data depositors and users.
- The provenance information and audit trails recorded for data and metadata processing and versioning.
- How the repository compares the essential properties of different versions of the same file.
- Identification checks for depositors.

Board Proposals: The Board proposes to include an example of what could be considered a good statement: a relational database maintains a timestamped record of metadata changes including which logged in account made the change, and welcomes community feedback.

Do you agree? Yes /No. If no give Community feedback box

Q18 - Deposit & Appraisal (R08)

R08. The repository accepts data and metadata based on defined criteria to ensure relevance and understandability for users.

Guidance:

The appraisal function during deposit is critical to evaluate whether digital objects meet all criteria for selection and to ensure appropriate management for their preservation. Appraisal ensures that deposited digital objects are relevant and are, or can become, understandable to the Designated Community.

The response statement and evidence should include references to the following items:

- Any documented deposit process that includes steps to ensure that data and metadata are sufficient for long-term preservation.
- A collection development policy or procedures to guide the selection of digital objects.
- Criteria for prioritisation and any different curation-levels or preservation levels defined during appraisal.
- The approach to digital objects that do not fall within the mission/collection profile.
- Procedures to determine that the metadata required to interpret and use the digital objects are provided.
- Any automated assessment of metadata adherence to relevant schemas.
- The repository approach if metadata provided is insufficient for long-term preservation.
- A list of preferred formats.
- Checks in place to ensure that depositors adhere to the preferred formats.
- The approach towards digital objects that are deposited in non-preferred formats.
- The transfer of custody and responsibility during the handover from the depositor to the repository.

This Requirement covers the selection criteria applied at the point of deposit. Data Quality (R11) should be used to address steps taken by the repository during the curation process.

Board Proposals: The Board suggests to change the words “understandability” and “understandable” to “accessibility” and “accessible”, and welcomes community feedback.

Do you agree? Yes /No. If no give Community feedback box

Q19 - Preservation plan (R09)

R09. The repository assumes responsibility for long-term preservation and manages this function in a planned and documented way.

Guidance:

The repository, depositors, and Designated Community need to understand the level of responsibility undertaken for the long-term preservation of data and metadata. Procedures must be documented and their completion assured.

The response statement and evidence should include references to the following items:

- The documented approach to preservation, including whether this involves format migration, emulation, etc. Ensuring bit level integrity is vital but not sufficient for preservation. Ensuring bit level integrity is vital but not sufficient for preservation.
- File formats and metadata schemas for long term preservation.
- How the level of responsibility for the preservation of each item is defined.
- Plans related to future migrations or similar measures to address the threat of obsolescence.
- Actions relevant to preservation specified in documentation, including custody transfer, submission information criteria, and preservation information metadata.
- Measures to ensure these actions are taken.
- Any minimum stated retention and/or preservation periods.
- How often the digital objects are re-appraised and the possible outcomes of reappraisal.

- The repository approach to deleting/removing data and metadata from collection/holdings including the impact on persistent identifiers.

The rights of the repository, including the right to preserve, are covered under Rights Management (R02). Bit level integrity is covered under Storage and Integrity (R14). Acceptable file formats at deposit should be covered under Deposit and Appraisal (R08). Measures to ensure that file formats, schemas and content are appropriate to the Designated Community should be covered under Reuse (R13).

Board Proposals: The Board proposes to remove the duplicate text “Ensuring bit level integrity is vital but not sufficient for preservation”, and welcomes community feedback.

Do you agree? Yes /No. If no give Community feedback box

Q20 - Quality Assurance (R10)

R10. The repository addresses technical quality and standards compliance, and ensures that sufficient information is available for end users to make quality-related evaluations.

Guidance:

Different repositories undertake different levels of curation on data, metadata and documentation depending on the needs and expectations of their depositors and Designated Community. Quality assurance by the repository ensures that digital objects comply with a range of standard criteria including acceptable formats, metadata schema, metadata content and links to other digital objects. This relates to ‘technical quality’ rather than the ‘scientific quality’ of the original digital objects creation or collection prior to deposit, though the repository must ensure there is sufficient information about the digital objects for the Designated Community to assess their fitness for use. Data, or associated metadata, may have quality issues relevant to their research value, but this does not preclude their use if a user can make a well-informed decision on their suitability through provided documentation.

The response statement and evidence should include references to the following items:

- The approach to data and metadata quality taken by the repository including variations for different curation-levels.
- The standards that data, metadata and documentation must comply with to be acceptable for preservation and access. Whether these are general external standards, internally developed standards or specific to a community of practice.
- The quality control checks in place ensure the completeness and understandability of data and metadata.
- The approach to resolving issues e.g. whether the digital objects are returned to the depositor for rectification, fixed by the repository, noted by quality flags, and/or included in the accompanying metadata.
- The approach to managing changes to expected standards (e.g. new or updated data formats of metadata schemas) in response to changes in the technical environment or to changes in the needs of the Designated Community.
- Any links provided to other digital objects’ data and metadata e.g. related digital objects, publications, or the use of controlled vocabularies and ontologies.

This Requirement refers to data and metadata quality standards and assurance during curation. Selection criteria are covered during Deposit and Appraisal (R08). Measures to ensure that digital objects remain fit for purpose over time are covered under Preservation Plan (R09).

Board Proposals: None, the Board welcomes community feedback.

Do you agree? Yes /No. If no give Community feedback box

Q21 - Workflows (R11)

R11. Digital object management takes place according to defined workflows from deposit to access.

Guidance:

For Quality Assurance (R10) to be achieved, it is necessary to avoid ad hoc actions and to deliver consistency of practice for all digital objects and across repository functions. This requires that workflows be defined, documented, and change-managed. Workflows may be specified in a mixture of standard operating procedures, business process descriptions and diagrams that guide normal practice and provide mechanisms for handling exceptions.

The response statement and evidence should include references to the following items:

- Workflows/business process descriptions covering the curation levels performed.
- How workflows are adjusted for different types of data and metadata.
- Decision handling within the workflows.
- Change management of workflows.
- Ability to track workflow execution, with mechanisms to handle exceptions.

This Requirement confirms that all workflows are documented. It should be noted if there are different workflows for different levels of security mentioned in the Legal and Ethical (R04) response statement. Workflows may include qualitative and quantitative checking of outputs, but any detail on checks and compliance should be addressed under Quality Assurance (R10).

Board Proposals: None, the Board welcomes community feedback.

Do you agree? Yes /No. If no give Community feedback box

Q22 - Discovery and Identification (R12)

R12. The repository enables users to discover the digital objects and refer to them in a persistent way through proper citation.

Guidance:

Effective data and metadata sharing discovery is key to resource discovery. Once discovered, digital objects should be referenceable through full citations, including persistent identifiers (PIDs) to help ensure that they can be accessed into the future.

The response statement and evidence should include references to the following items:

- The search facilities offered by the repository.

- The standards that a searchable metadata catalogue complies with.
- The approach to ensuring that identifiers are unique and persistent.
- Machine harvesting of the metadata.
- Repository, or repository data and metadata, inclusion in disciplinary or generic registries of resources.
- Recommended data citations.

Applicants should describe their use of a third party persistent identifier system, or document their own approach to ensuring that identifiers remain globally unique and persistent. The use of a third party to support PID creation and resolution is not sufficient; applicants should describe how they ensure that identifiers continue to resolve to the correct data or metadata over time, including the version rules that guide when a new identifier is created for a digital object. Applicants that do not have a persistent identifier solution cannot achieve “Implemented: the requirement has been fully implemented by the repository” for this requirement.

Board Proposals: None, the Board welcomes community feedback.

Do you agree? Yes /No. If no give Community feedback box

Q23 - Reuse (R13)

R13. The repository enables reuse of the digital objects over time, ensuring that appropriate information is available to support understanding and use.

Guidance:

Repositories must ensure that data and metadata continue to be understood and used effectively into the future despite changes in technology and the Designated Community's knowledge base. This Requirement evaluates the measures taken to ensure that data and metadata are reusable.

The response statement and evidence should include references to the following items:

- The ways in which the repository engages with their Designated Community of users to identify their needs.
- The data formats, metadata schemas, controlled vocabularies and ontologies used to support reuse, and how these meet the community needs.
- The metadata and documentation provided at the point of access to support understandability and reuse appropriate to the Designated Community. This may include information specific to data type, e.g. manuals, calibration records, photos, protocols.
- Measures to ensure that data and metadata remain understandable.
- Management of changes to data, metadata, documentation or other information that supports reuse.

Responses to this Requirement should focus on engagement with the Designated Community, identification of their needs and specifying how their needs are met.

Board Proposals: None, the Board welcomes community feedback.

Do you agree? Yes /No. If no give Community feedback box

Q24 - Information Technology & Security

Storage & Integrity (R14)

R14. The repository applies documented processes to ensure data and metadata storage and integrity.

Guidance:

In addition to maintaining 'archival' copies of digital objects, repositories need to store data and metadata from the point of deposit, for curation and preservation, and for access by users. For each storage location, measures should be in place to ensure that unintentional or unauthorised changes can be detected and correct versions of data and metadata recovered.

The response statement and evidence should include references to the following items:

- Processes and documents to ensure that the repository staff have a clear understanding of all storage locations and how they are managed.
- The repository's strategy for multiple copies.
- The risk management techniques used to inform the strategy.
- Procedures for handling and monitoring deterioration of storage media.
- Procedures to ensure that data and metadata are only deleted as part of an approved and documented process.
- Any checks (i.e. fixity checks) used to verify that a digital object has not been altered or corrupted from deposit to use.

Storage and integrity measures should be covered here (R14) and not as part of Technical Infrastructure (R15) or Security (R16) responses. Details of how intentional changes to the data and metadata are logged should be covered under Provenance & Authenticity (R07).

Board Proposals: None, the Board welcomes community feedback.

Do you agree? Yes /No. If no give Community feedback box

Q25 - Technical Infrastructure (R15)

R15. The repository is managed on well-supported operating systems and other core infrastructural software and hardware appropriate to the services it provides to its Designated Community.

Guidance:

Repositories must operate on reliable and stable core infrastructure that maximises service availability. The details of technical infrastructure will vary widely across repositories. Responses and evidence should focus on demonstrating that the repository solution, including hardware and software is well managed and appropriate to the needs of the repository functions and the Designated Community of users.

The response statement and evidence should include references to the following items:

- The repository software used for deposit, curation, preservation and access management.

Whether it is community supported, open source, or locally developed.

- Any IT service management approach followed and the functions this approach specifies (e.g. systems documentation, software inventories, code repositories, infrastructure development planning).
- Any international, community or other technical infrastructure standards in place and how compliance is monitored.
- The version control systems used for repository generated software.
- Measures taken to ensure that availability, bandwidth, and connectivity are sufficient to meet the needs of the Designated Community.
- Processes in place to monitor and manage the need for technical change, including in response to the changing needs of Preservation (R10), and Reuse (R13) by the Designated Community.

Technical aspects of business continuity, disaster recovery and succession planning are relevant here, but their management should be covered under Continuity of Service (R03). This requirement excludes Security (R16) measures and Storage & Integrity (R14).

File formats and metadata schema information should be referenced under Deposit & Appraisal (R08) and Reuse (R13). Standards that are not technical or security focussed should be referenced under Quality Assurance (R10).

Board Proposals: None, the Board welcomes community feedback.

Do you agree? Yes /No. If no give Community feedback box

Q26 - Security (R16)

R16. The repository protects the facility and its data, metadata, products, services, and users.

Guidance:

The repository should analyze potential threats, assess risks, and create a consistent security system. It should consider damage scenarios based on malicious actions, human error, or technical failure that pose a threat to the repository and its data, metadata, products, services, and users. It should measure the likelihood and impact of such scenarios, decide which risk levels are acceptable, and determine which measures should be taken to counter the threats to the repository and its Designated Community. This should be an ongoing process.

The response statement and evidence should include references to the following items:

- The levels of security required for different data and metadata and environments, and how these are supported.
- The IT security system, employees with roles related to security (e.g. security officers), and any risk analysis approach in use.
- Measures in place to protect the facility. How the premises where digital objects are held are secured.
- Any security-specific standards the repository references or complies with.
- Any authentication and authorization procedures employed to securely manage access to systems in use.

Responses should not cover Storage and Integrity (R14) measures or the wider Technical Infrastructure (R15).

Board Proposals: None, the Board welcomes community feedback.

Do you agree? Yes /No. If no give Community feedback box